

Azo-oxime-carboxylates of bivalent platinum

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The tridentate ligands, H_2L have been used to synthesize complexes of type $[Pt(PPh_3)L]$ and $[Pt(n-BuNH_2)L]$. Spectroscopic and X-ray diffractometric studies were utilized for their characterization.

The ability of *cis*-platin to block DNA replication and cell division¹ was at first reported by Rosenberg and subsequently its use as a potent anti-tumour agent^{2,3} has influenced tremendously the development of co-ordination chemistry of platinum⁴. One of the major drawbacks of the use of *cis*-platin in chemotherapy is its hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity⁵ and in order to reduce its toxic effects, certain other anti-tumour drugs have been devised where carboxylate ligands are bound to bivalent platinum. These drugs are referred to as second generation platinum anti-tumour drugs of which Pt-CBDCA, **1**^{6,7} and Pt-EtMaL, **2**⁷ are very promising.

The enhanced interest of the platinum carboxylates due to their anti-blastoma activity led us to synthesize square planar platinum(II) complexes using a tridentate⁸⁻¹⁰ ligand containing carboxyl group in conjunction with azo and oxime function (H_2L , **3**). The synthetic procedure of

H_2L^1 , Ar = phenyl
 H_2L^2 , Ar = *p*-tolyl
 H_2L^3 , Ar = α -naphthyl
 H_2L **3**

the complexes of type $[Pt(PPh_3)L]$ and $[Pt(n-BuNH_2)L]$, along with their characterization are reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

The 1 : 1 : 1 reaction of K_2PtCl_4 with H_2L (three ligands are used in the present work) and triphenyl phosphine in heterogenous water-dichloromethane medium at RT leads to the formation of blue-green complexes of type $[Pt(PPh_3)L]$ (eq. 1). In a similar type of reaction, if *n*-butyl amine is used instead of triphenyl phosphine, we ended up with green complexes of type $[Pt(n-BuNH_2)L]$ (eq. 2). Both the above two types of complexes are uni-

formly diamagnetic, (d^8 system) revealing their square planar geometry. They absorb at around 500–525 nm in dichloromethane solution. The IR spectra of $[Pt(PPh_3)L]$ complexes are characterized by two stretches in the region 500–700 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of triphenyl phosphine¹¹. On the other hand, the $[Pt(n-BuNH_2)L]$ type of complexes exhibit symmetric and anti-symmetric N-H stretches¹² in the region 3300–3500 cm^{-1} (Table 1).

The X-ray structure of $[Pt(PPh_3)L^2]$ has not been determined but its cell parameters (Table 2) are analogous to those of $[Pd(PPh_3)L^2]$ ⁹, suggesting that $[Pt(PPh_3)L^2]$ and $[Pd(PPh_3)L^2]$ are isomorphous. Thus $[Pt(PPh_3)L]$ complexes have the gross geometry, **4**. Similar considerations⁹ and also from the (CHN) analysis, the geometry of $[Pt(n-BuNH_2)L]$ can be represented by **5**.

Table 1. Spectral data of the complexes

Compd. (Colour)	UV-vis data λ_{\max} nm (log ϵ)	IR data, cm^{-1}	
		ν_{NH_2}	ν_{PPh_3}
[Pt(PPh ₃)L ¹] ^a (Blue green)	525 (3.498), 370 ^b (3.618)	–	515, 705
[Pt(PPh ₃)L ²] ^a (Blue green)	520 (3.512), 370 ^b (3.598)	–	505, 700
[Pt(PPh ₃)L ³] ^a (Blue green)	510 (3.482), 370 ^b (3.604)	–	510, 700
[Pt(n-BuNH ₂)L ¹] ^a (Green)	500 (3.714), 450 ^b (2.944), 360 ^b (3.810)	3355, 3425	–
[Pt(n-BuNH ₂)L ²] ^a (Green)	505 (3.642), 450 ^b (2.712), 360 ^b (3.784)	3340, 3430	–
[Pt(n-BuNH ₂)L ³] ^a (Green)	505 (3.724), 450 ^b (2.882), 360 ^b (3.865)	3350, 3440	–

^aIn dichloromethane, ^bShoulder.

Table 2. Cell parameters for [Pt(PPh₃)L²]

Empirical formula	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₃ Pt
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.34 × 0.30 × 0.32
a, Å	9.173 (4)
b, Å	16.530 (10)
c, Å	23.293 (11)
v, Å ³	3518 (3)
Crystal system	Monoclinic

4

5

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-1601 PC spectrophotometer was used to record UV-vis spectra and the IR spectra were recorded in a KBr disk on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibilities at RT were measured using a PAR-155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L75BAL magnet. A Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series (II) elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (CHN).

Crystals of [Pt(PPh₃)L²] (0.28 × 0.30 × 0.34 mm) were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into the dichloromethane solution. The cell parameters of this complex were determined by least-squares fit of 30 machine centred reflections ($2\theta = 15\text{--}30^\circ$) on a Siemens R3m/V four circle diffractometer with graphite monochromated MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) and are

listed in Table 2.

The ligands, H₂L were prepared by reported methods¹⁰ and the platinum complexes were synthesized by a general method, the details of one representative cases are described below. Solvent and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources.

((2-Carboxylatophenyl)azo)benzaldoximatotriphenylphosphineplatinum(II), [Pt(PPh₃)L¹]:

An aqueous solution (25 cm³) of K₂PtCl₄ (200 mg, 0.48 mmol) was added dropwise to a dichloromethane solution (25 cm³) of H₂L¹ (130 mg, 0.48 mmol) and triphenyl phosphine (0.126 mg, 0.48 mmol). The contents were allowed to stir at RT for 2 h when the aqueous layer became colourless. The green organic layer was separated and reduced to 5 cm³ when the green crystalline precipitate of the complex was obtained. It was then filtered, washed with water and finally dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂ (yield : 84%) (Found : C, 52.94; H, 3.28; N, 5.86. Required for [Pt(PPh₃)L¹] (C₃₂H₂₄N₃O₃ Pt) : C, 53.04; H, 3.34; N, 5.80%). The complexes [Pt(PPh₃)L²] and [Pt(PPh₃)L³] were synthesized by analogous procedures (Found : C, 53.58; H, 3.49; N, 5.75. Required for [Pt(PPh₃)L²] (C₃₃H₂₆N₃O₃ Pt) : C, 53.66; H, 3.55; N, 5.69%) (Found : C, 55.75; H, 3.36; N, 5.38. Required for [Pt(PPh₃)L³] (C₃₆H₂₆N₃O₃ Pt) : C, 55.82; H, 3.38; N, 5.42%).

((2-Carboxylatophenyl)azo)benzaldoximatobutylamineplatinum(II), [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L¹]:

To 25 cm³ of dichloromethane solution of H₂L¹ (130 mg, 0.48 mmol) and n-butylamine (1 drop) an aqueous solution of K₂PtCl₄ (200 mg, 0.48 mmol) was added dropwise. The contents were magnetically stirred at RT for 2 h when the aqueous layer became colourless. The intense green organic layer was separated and evaporated to 5 ml when the green crystalline precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with hexane and finally dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂ (yield : 76%) (Found : C, 40.29; H, 3.74; N, 10.53. Required for [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L¹] (C₁₈H₂₀N₄O₃ Pt) : C, 40.38; H, 3.76; N, 10.46%). The complexes [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L²] and [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L³] were prepared by similar method (Found : C, 41.59; H, 4.06; N, 10.12. Required for [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L²] (C₁₉H₂₂N₄O₃ Pt) : C, 41.53; H, 4.04; N, 10.20%) (Found : C, 44.05; H, 3.77; N, 9.49. Required for [Pt(n-BuNH₂)L³] (C₂₂H₂₂N₄O₃ Pt) : C, 45.13; H, 3.79; N, 9.57%).

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References

1. B. Rosenberg and L. Vancamp, *Nature*, 1965, **205**, 698.
2. B. Rosenberg, L. Vancamp, J. E. Trosko and V. H. Mansour, *Nature*, 1969, **222**, 385; H. M. Pinedo and J. H. Schornagel (eds.), "Platinum and other Metal Coordination Compounds in Cancer Chemotherapy", Plenum Press, New York, 1990; S. J. Lippard and J. M. Berg, "Principles of Bioinorganic Chemistry", University Science Books, Mill Valley, California, 1994.
3. G. N. Mukherjee and A. Das, "Elements of Bioinorganic Chemistry", U. N. Dhar and Sons Pvt. Ltd., Kolkata, 1993.
4. B. Lippert, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **182**, 263.
5. P. A. Chaloner, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **101**, 83 and references therein.
6. I. S. Krull, X. D. Ding, C. Selavka and F. Hochberg, *Methodol. Surv. Biochem. Anal.*, 1984, **14**, 139.
7. A. Saudek, H. Piveoá, D. Nasková and J. Drosnik, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1985, **24**, 13; H. Pivcová, A. Saudek, D. Nasková and J. Drosnik, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1985, **23**, 43.
8. S. Ganguly, S. Karmakar and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 116; S. Ganguly and S. Karmakar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 335.
9. C. K. Pal, S. Karmakar and S. Ganguly, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 90.
10. S. Karmakar and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **35**, 1935; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 85.
11. S. Bhattacharya, S. Banerjee, B. K. Dirghangi, M. Menon and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 155; I. Chakravorty, S. Bhattacharya, S. Banerjee, B. K. Dirghangi and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 3747.